

SPECIMEN BANKING IN THE NATIONAL STATUS AND TRENDS PROGRAM:
DEVELOPMENT OF PROTOCOLS AND FIRST YEAR RESULTS

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ABSTRACT

The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration has initiated a Specimen Bank for estuarine and coastal samples, as part of its National Status and Trends Program. During the first year, sample collection protocols were developed for the collection of benthic fish, bivalve molluscs, and associated sediments. Specimens, from over 40 sites nationwide, have now been submitted for inclusion in the Specimen Bank which is housed at the National Bureau of Standards in Gaithersburg, Maryland. Specimens are preserved at liquid nitrogen temperature with degradation expected to be minimal for decades. Retrospective analysis of specimens will allow the opportunity to derive baseline values for new environmental contaminants and make historical marine samples available for analysis when new and improved analytical procedures become available. Preliminary analyses of selected samples collected during the first year are presently under way for organic and trace element contaminants.

1. INTRODUCTION

Prior to the 1970's, the idea of retrospective analysis prompted experiments comparing chemical constituents in environmental materials incidentally preserved with current samples. In the 1960's, for example, pollution was studied in Sweden by researchers who compared chemical constituents of recent samples of bird tissues with that of bird skins preserved in academic and museum collections dating from 1840 (1). In the 1960's, the kepone content in shellfish and sediments from the James River (Virginia) was similarly determined and compared with banked tissue samples to establish the earliest date of this chemical's occurrence in the river (2).

Now, the concept of specimen banking for archiving and retrospective analyses of biological

samples is widely recognized as an important element of systematic environmental monitoring and international workshops [1977, 1978, and 1982] (3,4,5) have repeatedly recommended the establishment of specimen banking programs for environmental monitoring. In response to these recommendations and the growing worldwide concern for monitoring the health of the environment, a number of countries have established formal specimen banking programs including the United States, the Federal Republic of Germany, Japan, Canada, and Sweden.

In the United States, a pilot Environmental Specimen Bank Program was established in 1980 at the National Bureau of Standards (NBS), sponsored in part by the Environmental Protection Agency. Other Federal agencies, including the Food and Drug Administration, Department of Agriculture, National Cancer Institute, and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), of which the Ocean Assessments Division is a part, have joined in specimen banking activities at NBS.

In Fiscal Year 1984, NOAA's Ocean Assessments Division (OAD) initiated a new program called the National Status and Trends (NS&T) Program, within which a series of activities are being undertaken to quantify the current status and long-term temporal and spatial trends of key contaminant concentrations and biological indicators of contaminant effects in the nation's coastal and estuarine environments (6). The program's purposes are to provide highly reliable data on concentrations of toxic chemicals in marine fish, shellfish, and sediments; to measure biologic parameters that accurately reflect anthropogenic stress; and to assess marine environmental quality and recommend Federal actions needed to maintain or to improve it. One of the elements of the NS&T Program is the archival of samples for retrospective analyses.

The methods of collection, preparation, and storage of samples for a specimen banking program are critical to the scientific accuracy of the analytical data comparison. The methods used in the specimen banking component of the NOAA NS&T Program are described in this paper.

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2. NS&T CRYOGENIC STORAGE FACILITY

Because of its long-term experience with cryogenic specimen storage and related specimen banking activities, the NBS was selected for the NS&T Specimen Bank. The facilities available at NBS for storage of NS&T materials include a Class-100 clean-air laboratory designed to minimize sample contamination from the laboratory environment during sample handling, processing, and storage. The laboratory has two sections, one for trace element analysis and the other for trace organic analysis. An additional room has been designed for long-term storage of environmental and biological samples and contains the NS&T liquid nitrogen vapor freezer whose volumetric capacity of 500 liters can be maintained at temperatures ranging from -110 to -150°C (Figure 1).

The NBS facility presently receives samples from two NS&T activities--the Benthic Surveillance Project and the Mussel Watch Project. Each year benthic fish (muscle and liver tissue) and sediment samples collected from 10 of the 50 coastal and estuarine sites nationwide in the Benthic Surveillance Project are being archived along with bivalve molluscs and sediments from 30 of 150 sites nationwide in the Mussel Watch Project (Figure 2).

Figure 1

Figure 2

Specimen Bank Sampling Sites - 1986
Mussel Watch Project

In the past, various storage temperatures have been used to preserve environmental samples and a number of problems have been encountered. Work by Canadian investigators has shown ice crystal formation and sample dessication for container-stored samples maintained at -25°C; animal tissues wrapped in aluminum foil stored at -30°C also showed degradation (7). Analyses of mussel tissue stored by Japanese investigators showed a reduction of dimethylnitrosoamine by 50% after storage at -20°C for two years (8).

Numerous laboratories have experimented with -85°C as a storage temperature but results are inconclusive (9). The optimum storage temperatures appear to be below -135°C. These temperatures are easily maintained by liquid nitrogen freezers. Liquid nitrogen freezers have an added advantage over compression freezers, since they do not lose cooling ability during electric power failures. Therefore, liquid nitrogen freezers have been selected for the NS&T Specimen Bank.

3. BENTHIC SURVEILLANCE SPECIMEN BANKING PROTOCOLS

Protocols for taking, handling, preparing, and storing of samples for the NS&T Program are designed to ensure optimum "storability" in terms of noncontamination and adequacy of sample weight and to permit scientific accuracy of eventual analysis. Separate sample collection and handling protocols were developed for the two NS&T Projects (10): Benthic Surveillance and Mussel Watch.

For the Benthic Surveillance Project two replicate aliquots of 150g each were collected for both benthic fish liver and muscle tissue. Replicate samples of sediments were taken from the same sites.

To ensure that tissues were not contaminated, fish were necropsied in positive-pressure hoods using only specially cleaned materials and tools. For the dissection, two tool groups were used: one for the removal of the liver samples and the other for fish muscle collection. Each tool group in turn had two sub-sets. The first set of tools in each group was used to enter the sampling field, i.e., to cut through the body wall to access the body cavity (for liver) or to cut through the potentially contaminated epidermis (11) to sample fish muscle. The actual removal of the liver or muscle tissue occurred with the use of titanium knives. These knives were used to avoid the problem of iron and/or chromium contamination of samples.

Dissected tissue replicates were placed into pre-cleaned Teflon bags, which had been packaged under Class-100 clean room conditions, and then the bags were heat sealed and placed in a second bag and again heat sealed.

Special precautions were taken with the dissection tools both during a dissection and after the tools were cleaned. Before initiating a set of

dissections and after sharpening the titanium knives, the tools were wiped of extraneous material, scrubbed in a detergent solution, rinsed with tap water followed by a distilled water rinse and finally transferred to a fume exhaust hood where they were carefully rinsed with methylene chloride.

For the Benthic Surveillance Project, two replicate sediment aliquots of 150g each were also taken at each site. Samples were collected with the use of a box corer. Two 50g subsamples, (replicates A&B) were taken using Teflon cylindrical corers from each of three sampled stations per site. These were then composited in Teflon bags to yield two duplicate 150g composites per site.

The NS&T Program's Mussel Watch Project also supplied duplicates of bivalve and sediment samples from 30 sites nationwide. Each site consisted of three stations; each station provided two batches of approximately 16-18 mussels (*Mytilus edulis*/*M. californianus*) or two batches of 10 oysters (*Crassostrea virginica*) for a total of approximately 100 mussels or 60 oysters per site (Figure 3). After collection, the bivalves were sorted for size on a noncontaminating tray and then rinsed with seawater and scrubbed with a noncontaminating brush. Bivalves were finally divided into two batches and then sealed in Teflon bags for storage. Sediment samples for the Mussel Watch Project were handled in the same manner as for the Benthic Surveillance work.

Figure 3

Bivalve Specimen Bank Sampling Schematic samples are taken at 10 sites/coast

Pooled "A" replicates from each station or site = 30 oysters or 50 mussels

Pooled "B" replicates from each station or site = 30 oysters or 50 mussels

To ensure that only a minimum of sample degradation occurred, Benthic Surveillance samples (fish tissues and sediments) were frozen in liquid nitrogen in the field. Due to logistical difficulties and the large sample volume, samples from the Mussel Watch Project were stored and shipped on dry ice before the final storage in liquid nitrogen freezers at the NBS.

Using a Teflon disk mill developed by the NBS, a portion of the tissue samples sent to the Specimen Bank are homogenized at cryogenic temperatures. Cryogenic homogenization reduces loss of volatile components and reduces the likelihood of changes in sample composition due to thawing and refreezing. Experiments with mussel tissue indicate that after homogenization, virtually all the frozen material passes through a 0.46 mm mesh sieve (12).

Teflon is the substance of choice for field sampling equipment and storage containers, e.g., Teflon-coated forceps and sediment scoops, and Teflon storage bags and sediment corers. Properties that make Teflon the preferred material for this equipment are: reduced chance of contaminating samples with trace elements (other than carbon and fluorine), and a chemical inertness that can withstand cleaning procedures with acid and organic solvents (13).

4. ANALYSES

The NS&T Program is quantifying the concentration of aromatic hydrocarbons (19 compounds), chlorinated organics (16 compounds) including polychlorinated biphenyls (8 congener groups) and trace elements (17 elements). Using the following methods, the NBS will supply the NS&T Program with data for the Specimen Banking portion of the program.

For the determination of these organic contaminants, the sample homogenate is first mixed with precleaned anhydrous sodium sulfate and internal standards are added. The sodium sulfate mixture is then Soxhlet extracted using methylene chloride. The fractions containing the aromatic hydrocarbons, polychlorinated biphenyls, and chlorinated organics are isolated using a silica microfractionation column, gel permeation column, and finally an aminosilane liquid chromatographic column. The concentrated fractions are analyzed by gas chromatography using flame ionization detection or liquid chromatography using fluorescence detection for the aromatic hydrocarbons and by gas chromatography using electron capture detection for the polychlorinated biphenyls and chlorinated organics (13).

Selected trace elements will be determined in the sediment and tissue samples using a combination of instrumental neutron activation analysis and x-ray fluorescence analyses. The combination of these two techniques has been demonstrated to provide data for 44 elements in bivalve samples (14).

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